

Organotypic and microphysiological human tissue models for translational toxicology and pharmacology

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Abstract

The number of successful drug development projects has been stagnant for decades despite major breakthroughs in chemistry, molecular biology and genomics. Unreliable translation of preclinical *in vitro* and *in vivo* models has been identified as a major cause. Organotypic and microphysiological culture of primary human cells has emerged as a promising set of tools for preclinical drug development to narrow this translation gap. In this talk I will provide an overview of our recent efforts in developing 3D human tissue cultures and microfluidic models for both efficacy and safety assessments. In addition, the talk will present recent use cases where the use of such organotypic cultures has had direct impacts on market authorizations.